

Lung Area Localization in Chest X-ray Images Using Progressive Distance-Based Masking and Anatomical Patterns

Fairuztsani Kemal Setiawan
School of Computing
Telkom University
Bandung, Indonesia
fairuztsn@student.telkomuniversity.ac.id

Abstract—Chest X-ray (CXR) remains one of the most prevalent medical imaging modalities for evaluating pulmonary conditions. However, automated localization of the lung area continues to face significant challenges due to low contrast and the complexity of overlapping anatomical structures. This study proposes an unsupervised approach for lung localization by leveraging progressive masking based on distance information (distance thresholding) and the periodic characteristics of rib patterns.

The proposed method was evaluated using 246 images from the JSRT dataset. Experimental results demonstrate stable performance with a mean Intersection over Union (IoU) score of 0.58 and high centroid localization precision, indicated by a mean Distance-IoU (DIoU) margin of less than 0.02 relative to the IoU. Analysis of detection characteristics revealed a dominant undersizing bias (present in 80.08% of the data), which is a consequence of the method’s conservative nature in core mask formation. Nonetheless, the method proved effective in generating spatially stable core regions free from topological leakage without requiring any training data. These findings provide a robust foundation for the future development of shape-based lung boundary estimation methods.

Index Terms—Chest X-ray, lung localization, unsupervised segmentation, anatomical masking, IoU, scale factor analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chest X-ray (CXR) is one of the most widely utilized medical imaging modalities in clinical practice for evaluating pulmonary conditions, such as infections, structural abnormalities, and chronic lung diseases [1]. In various medical image analysis systems, the localization of the lung area serves as a crucial preliminary stage, as the quality of localization directly influences the performance of subsequent analysis methods, including lung boundary segmentation and region-based feature extraction [3].

Nevertheless, accurate localization of the lung area remains a significant challenge. The primary obstacles include low contrast between lung tissues and surrounding structures, inter-individual anatomical variations, and the presence of overlapping non-pulmonary structures such as the ribs and the heart. Intensity-based or region-based segmentation methods frequently suffer from topological leakage, where the lung area is not properly sequestered from the background or non-

pulmonary structures due to similarities in intensity distribution [2].

Various approaches have been proposed to address these issues, ranging from rule-based methods to supervised learning and deep learning techniques. While learning-based approaches have shown promising performance, these methods are heavily dependent on the availability of large-scale annotated datasets [4], which in practice are difficult to obtain and require substantial cost and medical expertise. On the other hand, traditional rule-based methods tend to be sensitive to image variations and lack robustness against changes in imaging conditions.

To overcome these limitations, this study proposes an unsupervised approach for lung area localization in chest X-ray images. This approach utilizes a stepwise masking process designed to progressively narrow down candidate lung regions by integrating distance information via distance transform and anatomical pattern characteristics [5]. The primary focus of this method is the formation of a spatially stable core lung region that minimizes topological leakage.

The main contributions of this research are as follows:

- 1) Development of a lung localization method based on progressive masking without the requirement for annotated training data.
- 2) Utilization of distance-based information to form a core lung region that is robust against topological leakage.
- 3) Integration of anatomical pattern analysis (rib periodicity) for the selection of representative lung components.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research regarding the segmentation and localization of the lungs in chest X-ray images has evolved rapidly over the past few decades. In general, existing approaches can be classified into three primary categories: traditional image processing methods, deep learning-based methods, and methods utilizing distance information or geometric features.

A. Traditional Image Processing Methods

Early approaches relied heavily on techniques such as thresholding, morphological operations, and deformable mod-

els [2]. Candemir et al. [1] proposed a lung segmentation method based on anatomical atlases combined with non-rigid registration to account for anatomical variations. Although these methods demonstrated satisfactory results, they often require manual initialization or rigid shape assumptions, rendering them less robust to significant pathological conditions.

A major drawback of these methods is topological leakage, where the lung boundaries "bleed" into surrounding areas due to low contrast at the diaphragm or mediastinum [3]. Furthermore, the dependency on structuring element sizes in morphological operations limits the flexibility of these methods when encountering inter-individual scale variations.

B. Deep Learning-Based Methods

Convolutional architectures, such as U-Net, have achieved high accuracy in medical image segmentation [4]. However, the performance of these models is highly dependent on the quality and quantity of ground truth annotations [6]. Moreover, deep learning models often experience performance degradation when evaluated on data from different hospitals or imaging devices (domain shift) due to a lack of generalization in the automatically learned features [7].

C. Distance-Based Approaches and Structural Characteristics

The distance transform has long been utilized to identify the centroid or stable regions of an object [8]. In medical image processing, distance information facilitates the subtle separation of adjacent or touching objects.

Several studies have employed projection analysis to detect rib structures to assist in lung localization [9]. Rib periodicity patterns provide strong low-level information to distinguish the lung area from other soft tissues. However, the unsupervised integration of distance maps and periodicity pattern analysis to specifically mitigate topological leakage remains largely unexplored.

D. Research Gap

Based on the aforementioned review, a gap exists between the need for computationally lightweight, unsupervised methods and the capability to overcome topological leakage. Existing methods often face a trade-off between high accuracy (requiring large datasets) and ease of implementation (with compromised stability). This study addresses this gap by proposing a progressive masking mechanism that integrates the geometric stability of the distance transform with structural validation from anatomical periodicity patterns.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed method is an unsupervised approach for lung area localization in chest X-ray images. Overall, the system workflow consists of four main stages presented sequentially in Figure 1. These stages include image pre-processing, body mask extraction, distance-based core lung mask formation, and final component selection based on rib pattern periodicity analysis.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the proposed lung localization methodology, illustrating the transition from the input image to bounding box extraction through three primary phases.

This approach is designed to mitigate topological leakage and anatomical variations through a progressive masking process based on distance information and structural patterns. Generally, the method comprises three main phases: body mask extraction, core lung mask formation, and the selection of the most representative lung components.

A. Pre-processing

Given a grayscale chest X-ray image $I_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times W_0}$, the image is first resized to a fixed resolution:

$$I = \mathcal{R}(I_0), \quad I \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times 256} \quad (1)$$

To reduce noise and enhance local contrast, Gaussian smoothing and Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) are applied:

$$I_s = G_\sigma * I \quad (2)$$

$$I_c = \text{CLAHE}(I_s) \quad (3)$$

B. Phase 1: Body Mask Extraction

Initial segmentation is performed using coarse thresholding based on intensity percentiles:

$$M_0(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & I_c(x) > P_p(I_c) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where P_p denotes the p -th percentile of the intensity distribution of I_c .

To eliminate background artifacts connected to the image boundaries, morphological reconstruction is performed using markers from the boundary pixels:

$$M_r = \mathcal{R}_d(M_b, M_0) \quad (5)$$

where M_b is the marker initialized from the image borders.

The final body mask is defined as:

$$M_{\text{body}} = M_0 \wedge \neg M_r \quad (6)$$

This mask encompasses the entire body area and internal structures, including the lungs.

C. Phase 2: Distance-Based Core Lung Mask Formation

To reduce topological leakage between the lung area and the background, a minimum distance map is calculated for each background pixel $x \in \Omega_0$ relative to the body pixels or image boundaries.

By considering eight discrete directions \mathcal{D} , the minimum distance is defined as:

$$D(x) = \min_{d \in \mathcal{D}} d_g(x, \Omega_1 \cup \partial\Omega) \quad (7)$$

where:

- Ω_1 is the set of body pixels,
- $\partial\Omega$ is the image boundary,
- d_g is the discrete distance.

The distance map D yields high values in regions located far from the body boundaries, which empirically correlates with the core lung areas.

Instead of using a fixed threshold, segmentation is performed adaptively using global statistics:

$$\mu = \mathbb{E}[D], \quad \sigma = \sqrt{\text{Var}(D)} \quad (8)$$

The core lung mask is defined as:

$$M_{\text{core}}(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & D(x) \geq \mu + \alpha\sigma \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where $\alpha = 0.5$.

D. Phase 3: Lung Component Selection

Connected components from M_{core} are labeled and filtered based on a minimum area. For each candidate C_i , feature extraction based on rib patterns is conducted using the positive vertical gradient $G_y = \max(\partial I / \partial y, 0)$ projected in one dimension:

$$s_i(y) = \sum_x G_y(x, y) \quad (10)$$

The periodicity score S_i is calculated as the product of two components: peak density S_{peak} and autocorrelation strength S_{auto} . The first component measures the regularity of the inter-rib distance:

$$S_{\text{peak}}(s_i) = \frac{n}{\sigma_{\Delta} + \epsilon} \quad (11)$$

where n is the number of detected peaks and σ_{Δ} is the standard deviation of the peak-to-peak distances. The second component measures pattern repetition through normalized signal autocorrelation $\hat{s}_i(y) = s_i(y) - \bar{s}_i$:

$$S_{\text{auto}}(s_i) = \sum_{\tau=\tau_{\min}}^{\tau_{\max}} R_i(\tau), \quad R_i(\tau) = \frac{\sum_y \hat{s}_i(y) \cdot \hat{s}_i(y - \tau)}{\sum_y \hat{s}_i(y)^2} \quad (12)$$

The two components with the highest $S_i = S_{\text{peak}} \cdot S_{\text{auto}}$ scores are selected as the lung regions.

E. Algorithm Summary

Algorithm 1 Core Mask-Based Lung Localization

Require: Chest X-ray image I_0

Ensure: Lung mask M_{lung}

- 0: Resize I_0 to I
 - 0: Pre-processing $I \rightarrow I_c$
 - 0: Body mask extraction M_{body}
 - 0: Calculate distance map D
 - 0: Form core mask M_{core}
 - 0: Select lung components
 - 0: **return** $M_{\text{lung}} = 0$
-

F. Experimental Setup and Evaluation Metrics

To validate the performance of the proposed algorithm, experiments were conducted using the JSRT dataset. Since the algorithm output consists of area components, these are converted into bounding boxes to enable comparison with the ground truth.

1) *Mask to Bounding Box Conversion:* The lung localization representation is defined as a bounding box extracted from the extreme coordinates of the mask pixels:

$$B = [x_{\min}, y_{\min}, x_{\max}, y_{\max}] \quad (13)$$

where $x_{\min} = \min(x_{\text{mask}})$, and so forth. This process is applied to both the prediction results and the ground truth masks to ensure consistency in comparison.

2) *Performance Metrics:* Localization success is measured using two standard object detection metrics: Intersection over Union (IoU), which measures the degree of overlap between two boxes, and Distance-IoU (DIoU), which provides a penalty based on the distance between the centers of the two boxes.

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{Area}(B \cap B^{gt})}{\text{Area}(B \cup B^{gt})} \quad (14)$$

Where:

- $B \cap B^{gt}$ is the intersection area between the predicted box and the ground truth box.
- $B \cup B^{gt}$ is the union area between the two.

$$\text{DIoU} = \text{IoU} - \frac{\rho^2(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}^{gt})}{c^2} \quad (15)$$

Where:

- ρ is the Euclidean distance between the center points of boxes B and B^{gt} .
- \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{b}^{gt} denote the centroids of the respective boxes.
- c is the diagonal length of the smallest enclosing box (the smallest box that can contain both B and B^{gt} simultaneously).

Additionally, the Area Ratio (Scale Factor) is utilized to analyze potential size bias in the predictions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Quantitative Analysis of Localization Performance

The evaluation was conducted on 246 images from the JSRT dataset [10] (Kaggle version, 224×224 pixels). A statistical summary of the evaluation metrics is presented in Table I.

Table I
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF EVALUATION METRICS ($n = 246$)

Metric	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max
IoU (Left)	0.585	0.188	0.000	0.928
IoU (Right)	0.579	0.184	0.000	0.850
DIoU (Left)	0.572	0.214	-0.211	0.928
DIoU (Right)	0.562	0.229	-0.347	0.849
Scale (Left)	0.808	0.325	0.176	3.020
Scale (Right)	0.727	0.270	0.005	1.720

The mean IoU scores reside within the **0.58** range, indicating moderate localization capability. However, the proximity between the IoU and DIoU values (difference < 0.02) suggests that the algorithm achieves high centroid precision, even though the total area coverage remains suboptimal.

Figure 2. Distribution of Average IoU scores across the 246 images of the JSRT dataset.

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of Average IoU scores throughout the dataset. The distribution exhibits a left-skewed characteristic, with a dominant population concentrated within the 0.5 to 0.7 range. This indicates that the algorithm consistently surpasses the localization success threshold ($IoU \geq 0.5$), although the frequency of images reaching ideal values (> 0.8) remains limited. This distribution pattern reinforces the findings regarding the "undersize" bias, where the algorithm successfully identifies the lung location but fails to encompass the full anatomical area due to the conservative nature of the method.

B. Analysis of Size Bias and Detection Characteristics

The data reveals a predominant undersize bias, with 197 images (80.08%) producing bounding boxes smaller than the actual lung dimensions ($Scale < 0.9$). This stands in stark contrast to only 16 images exhibiting oversize characteristics.

Figure 3. Comprehensive visualization of lung localization results. Red dashed boxes represent the ground truth, while green boxes represent the algorithmic predictions. The first row displays five best cases with high overlap. The second row shows average cases dominated by the undersize phenomenon. The third row presents worst-case scenarios where the algorithm encountered detection failure.

These results are technically aligned with the methodology during the core mask formation stage, where distance thresholding and morphological erosion are employed to isolate lung candidates from other anatomical structures.

The left-skewed IoU distribution confirms that following the erosion phase, the algorithm lacks the capacity for sufficient re-expansion to reach the actual peripheral boundaries of the lungs, particularly in critical areas such as the apex and costophrenic angle. Consequently, while the centroid localization is accurate, the detected area tends to be smaller than the ground truth.

C. Discussion of Technical Factors and Failure Analysis

Based on the experimental results, several technical gaps between the initial development environment and the test dataset influenced performance:

- 1) **Resolution Discrepancy and Upscaling Effects:** The rib pattern autocorrelation method was developed and optimized using high-resolution images ($\approx 1000 \times 1000$ pixels). However, the JSRT dataset utilizes a lower resolution (224×224 pixels). Resizing to the target 256×256 pixels introduced upscaling artifacts that obscured the fine texture features of the ribs. This weakened the periodic signals required by the algorithm to precisely lock onto the outer lung boundaries.
- 2) **Component Agglomeration Anomalies (Greedy Detection):** Despite the dominance of undersizing, certain cases exhibited scale values surging up to 3.02. This occurred due to the failure of connected component separation, where a single prediction box (typically on the left side) became "greedy," encompassing a significant portion of the right lung area. This failure significantly reduced the IoU due to the substantial increase in False Positive areas.

- 3) **Centroid Stability vs. Boundary Expansion:** The stable DIOU values prove that the 8-way distance thresholding method is robust in determining the central location of the lungs. The primary issue lies in the final box expansion stage, which is overly conservative when processing low-resolution images.

This analysis suggests that performance limitations are primarily driven by resolution factors and the heuristic design of the final stage, rather than a failure in core lung localization.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

This study has successfully implemented an unsupervised method for lung area localization in chest X-ray images, utilizing a core mask approach and rib anatomical patterns. Based on the evaluation of 246 images from the JSRT dataset, the following key conclusions are drawn:

- 1) The algorithm demonstrates stable localization performance with a mean IoU score of 0.58. Although this value is categorized as moderate, the consistent DIOU values prove that the algorithm achieves high centroid positioning precision relative to the ground truth.
- 2) A dominant undersize bias was detected (80.08% of the dataset), which serves as a technical consequence of the conservative core mask formation phase designed to prevent topology leakage.
- 3) The use of low-resolution images (224×224 pixels) in the test dataset resulted in signal degradation of the rib features due to upscaling artifacts, which subsequently limited the expansion of the lung boundaries.

B. Recommendations (Future Works)

Several aspects identified for further development in future research include:

- 1) Evaluating the algorithm's performance across various input resolutions (e.g., 128×128) to determine the optimal balance between feature density and the reduction of interpolation noise.
- 2) Integrating active contour or level set methods in the post-processing stage to facilitate bounding box expansion toward more accurate lung edge gradients.
- 3) Optimizing autocorrelation parameters to be more adaptive to variations in medical image contrast, thereby preventing component merging (greedy detection) between the left and right lungs.

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